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¹ Document will be a draft until it was approved by the coordinator

² PU: Public, PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services), RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services), CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

³ The initials of the revising individual in capital letters

Deliverable D7.3

Tutor-web FarFish initial setup

29/11/2017

Executive Summary

This document reports progress and conclusions on deliverable D7.3, Tutor-web FarFish initial setup, in project FarFish. The report describes the launch of the FarFish part of www.tutor-web.net making available existing teaching material directed to the target audience. The material is made available in the tutor-web as a course, under the heading "Methods and techniques for data-limited fisheries." This course consists of multiple tutorials, providing material and drills at various stages of development, on topics from prerequisite mathematics, statistics and programming, through introductory fish population dynamics to methods for data-limited fisheries.

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1 Introduction

This document reports progress and conclusions on deliverable D7.3, Tutor-web FarFish initial setup, in project FarFish. The report describes the launch of the FarFish part of www.tutor-web.net making available existing teaching material directed to the target audience. The material is made available in the tutor-web as a course, under the heading "Methods and techniques for data-limited fisheries." This course provides material and drills on topics from prerequisite mathematics, statistics and programming, through introductory fish population dynamics to a draft of methods for data-limited fisheries.

The tutor-web system (Stefansson, 2004) has been developed to be a mobile-web system as described by Lentin *et al.* (2014). Within the tutor-web, courses consist of tutorials, which contain lectures. The hierarchy typically contains both material and drills on said material. The system has been used for teaching and educational research and has been demonstrated to enhance learning over and above general classroom instruction (Jonsdottir, 2017).

The system has been developed and enhanced so as to function in locations with unstable electricity and no Internet connection, both in remote areas (Stefansson, 2017) and even in isolated prisons (Njurai, 2017). The system uses a collection of methods to enhance student learning, from personalised drills through cryptocurrency rewards (Lentin and Stefansson, 2018).

The FarFish course initially consists of the following tutorials, described in subsections of the following chapter:

From numbers through algebra to calculus and linear algebra

Introduction to fish population dynamics

Applied multiple linear regression

Statistical stock assessment methods

Modelling length at age and length distributions

Principles of utilization: The precautionary approach

Methods and applications for data-limited fisheries

As project FarFish progresses, more material will be added to this course.

2 Current and proposed content of course on Methods and applications for data-limited fisheries

2.1 From numbers through algebra to calculus and linear algebra

2.1.1 Purpose

This tutorial is found as the first tutorial in <http://tutor-web.net/fish/fish850> and is composed of 33 lectures, consists of all the basics for a student to be able to comfortably take on general modelling tasks, whether in applied statistics or fishery science.

2.1.2 Prerequisites

This is considered a graduate-level course. A sufficient prerequisite is a BS/BA degree in any topic.

2.1.3 Current content

The course material consists of 171 pages on topics starting with basic arithmetic, moving on through programming using the R statistical package, vector arithmetic, matrices, mathematical functions, statistics and probability (discrete and continuous distribution), derivatives, integrals and multivariate distributions.

2.1.4 Drills

Each lecture contains one or more drills on the topics of the lecture. Currently each drill item is a multiple-choice question on the topics of the lecture.

Currently the tutorial contains a total of 235 drill items.

From numbers through algebra to calculus and linear algebra (math612.0)

by admin — last modified 2017-11-15 15:03 — [History](#)

Take a drill on Numbers, arithmetic and basic algebra [Download tutorial notes](#)

Lectures Literature Related courses Data files

- [Show raw tutorial TeX](#)
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Code	Name	Slide download	Num. slides	Num. questions
lecture110	Numbers, arithmetic and basic algebra	Download PDF	5	13
lecture120	Data vectors	Download PDF	5	11
lecture130	More on algebra	Download PDF	5	8
lecture140	Discrete random variables and the binomial distribution	Download PDF	7	6
lecture150	Functions	Download PDF	5	7
lecture160	Polynomials	Download PDF	6	10
lecture170	Simple data analysis in R	Download PDF	5	7
lecture180	Indices and the apply commands in R	Download PDF	6	5
lecture190	Functions of functions and the exponential function	Download PDF	6	9
lecture195	Inverse functions and the logarithm	Download PDF	6	9
lecture210	Continuity and limits	Download PDF	7	7
lecture220	Sequences and series	Download PDF	5	7
lecture230	Slopes of lines and curves	Download PDF	5	7
lecture240	Derivatives	Download PDF	8	7
lecture250	Applications of differentiation	Download PDF	6	7
lecture260	Integrals and probability density functions	Download PDF	6	7
lecture270	Principles of programming	Download PDF	8	8
lecture280	The Central Limit Theorem and related topics	Download PDF	3	7
lecture290	Miscellanea	Download PDF	3	7
lecture310	Multivariate probability distributions	Download PDF	6	7

Tutorial 1: From numbers through algebra to calculus and linear algebra

2.2 Introduction to fish population dynamics

2.2.1 Purpose

This tutorial is found as the second tutorial in <http://tutor-web.net/fish/fish850> and is composed of 6 lectures, providing a very basic introduction to fishery science.

2.2.2 Prerequisites

This is considered a graduate-level tutorial. A sufficient prerequisite is a BS/BA degree in any topic.

2.2.3 Current content

The material consists of 48 pages on topics starting with an introduction, moving on through data collection, biological measurements, basic data analyses and statistical sampling schemes.

2.2.4 Drills

Each lecture contains one or more drills on the topics of the lecture. Currently each drill item is a multiple-choice question on the topics of the lecture.

Currently the tutorial contains a total of 280 drill items.

The screenshot shows the FarFish interface for the tutorial 'Introduction to fish population dynamics (fish5101fishsci)'. The interface includes a navigation bar with 'Contents', 'View', 'Edit', and 'Sharing' options. Below the title, there are buttons for 'Take a drill on Introduction and overview' and 'Download tutorial notes'. A tabbed menu shows 'Lectures' as the active tab, with other tabs for 'Literature', 'Related courses', and 'Data files'. A list of actions includes 'Show raw tutorial TeX' and 'Update tutorial PDF'. A table lists the lecture content with columns for Code, Name, Slide download, Num. slides, and Num. questions.

Code	Name	Slide download	Num. slides	Num. questions
lecture10	Introduction and overview	Download PDF	12	6
lecture20	Collecting data for direct monitoring	Download PDF	11	174
lecture30	Use and design of biological samples	Download PDF	5	0
lecture40	Basic analysis of data	Download PDF	10	0
lecture50	Sampling	Download PDF	3	100
lecture60	Overview	Download PDF	1	0

Tutorial 2: Introduction to fish population dynamics

2.3 Applied multiple linear regression

2.3.1 Purpose

This tutorial is found as the third tutorial in <http://tutor-web.net/fish/fish850> and is composed of 5 lectures, providing important background to modelling by introducing the linear model in some detail. This forms an essential background for the nonlinear models used in fishery science.

2.3.2 Prerequisites

This is considered a graduate-level tutorial and requires completion of the previous two tutorials.

2.3.3 Current content

The material consists of 21 pages on multiple linear regression using R. This material will be expanded and rearranged during the development of the FarFish project.

2.3.4 Drills

Each lecture contains one or more drills on the topics of the lecture. Currently each drill item is a multiple-choice question on the topics of the lecture.

Currently the tutorial contains a total of 205 drill items.

Applied multiple linear regression (stats544-2-amulreg)

by [admin](#) — last modified 2014-09-18 10:49 — [History](#)

Take a drill on Multiple linear regression background

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Lectures
Literature
Related courses
Data files

- [Show raw tutorial TeX](#)
- [Update tutorial PDF](#)

Code	Name	Slide download	Num. slides	Num. questions
lecture30	Multiple linear regression background	Download PDF	0	101
lecture40	Multiple linear regression	Download PDF	0	101
lecture50	Deviations from assumptions	Download PDF	0	1
lecture60	Extensions to the multiple linear regression model	Download PDF	0	1
lecture70	Case studies	Download PDF	0	1

Tutorial 3: Applied multiple linear regression

2.4 Statistical stock assessment methods

2.4.1 Purpose

This tutorial is found as the fourth tutorial in <http://tutor-web.net/fish/fish850> and is composed of 8 lectures, describing the basics methods for modelling fish population dynamics.

2.4.2 Prerequisites

This is considered a graduate-level tutorial and depends on all the preceding tutorials.

2.4.3 Current content

The course material consists of 30 pages on topics on general stock assessment methods, from dynamic bulk production models through age-based dynamic models, nonlinear fitting methods and case studies.

2.4.4 Drills

Each lecture contains one or more drills on the topics of the lecture. Currently each drill is a multiple-choice question on the topics of the lecture.

Currently the tutorial contains a total of 200 drill items.

Statistical stock assessment methods (fish5108statass)

by Eva Dogg Steingrimsdottir — last modified 2016-12-19 11:41 — [History](#)

Take a drill on Statistical techniques for stock assessments

 Download tutorial notes

Lectures Literature Related courses Data files

- [Show raw tutorial TeX](#)
- [Update tutorial PDF](#)

Code	Name	Slide download	Num. slides	Num. questions
lecture10	Statistical techniques for stock assessments	Download PDF	3	99
lecture20	Production models	Download PDF	6	99
lecture30	Fitting criteria	Download PDF	6	0
lecture40	Formal statistical stock assessments in dynamic bulk production model	Download PDF	5	0
lecture50	Case studies of stock-production models	Download PDF	4	0
lecture60	Models with internal age structure	Download PDF	11	0
lecture70	Finicky details	Download PDF	5	0
lecture80	Some case studies	Download PDF	2	1

Tutorial 4: Statistical stock assessment methods

2.5 Modelling length at age and length distributions

2.5.1 Purpose

This tutorial is found as the fifth tutorial in <http://tutor-web.net/fish/fish850> and is composed of 8 lectures, designed to move the students on from basic knowledge towards techniques applicable for modelling population dynamics for data limited fisheries.

2.5.2 Prerequisites

This is considered a graduate-level tutorial and depends on all the preceding tutorials.

2.5.3 Current content

The course material consists of 36 pages on topics starting with models to describe growth and length distributions, including population models based on length distributions as well as methods to extract cohort information from length distributions.

2.5.4 Drills

Each lecture contains one or more drills on the topics of the lecture. Currently each drill item is a multiple-choice question on the topics of the lecture.

Currently the tutorial contains a total of 34 drill items.

Modelling length at age and length distributions (fish5103growth)
 by Eva Dagg Steingrimsdottir — last modified 2016-12-19 11:37 — [History](#)

Take a drill on Lack of age data - background [Download tutorial notes](#)

Lectures Literature Related courses Data files

- [Show raw tutorial TeX](#)
- [Update tutorial PDF](#)

Code	Name	Slide download	Num. slides	Num. questions
lecture10	Lack of age data - background	Download PDF	4	7
lecture20	Growth models	Download PDF	6	1
lecture30	Models of length distributions	Download PDF	13	6
lecture40	Case studies in analysis of length data	Download PDF	4	10
lecture50	Length-weight relationships	Download PDF	1	0
lecture60	Modelling the development of a length distribution	Download PDF	7	7
lecture70	Using length data in population models	Download PDF	2	1
lecture80	Using length data in population models	Download PDF	1	0

Tutorial 5: Modelling length at age and length distributions

2.6 Principles of utilization: The precautionary approach

2.6.1 Purpose

This tutorial is found as the sixth tutorial in <http://tutor-web.net/fish/fish850> and is composed of 4 lectures. These form a draft introduction to the precautionary approach and will be expanded during the project.

2.6.2 Prerequisites

This is considered a graduate-level tutorial and uses concepts of sustainability and the like, as obtained from earlier tutorials.

2.6.3 Current content

The material consists of 19 pages on the precautionary approach to utilising marine resources.

2.6.4 Drills

Each lecture contains one or more drills on the topics of the lecture. Currently each drill is a multiple-choice question on the topics of the lecture.

Currently the tutorial contains a placeholder of 2 drill items, to be expanded during the project.

Principles of utilization: The precautionary approach (fish5109pa)
 by Eva Dögg Steingrimsdóttir — last modified 2016-12-19 11:41 — [History](#)

Take a drill on Principles of utilization Download tutorial notes

Lectures Literature Related courses Data files

- [Show raw tutorial TeX](#)
- [Update tutorial PDF](#)

Code	Name	Slide download	Num. slides	Num. questions
lecture10	Principles of utilization	Download PDF	3	1
lecture20	Reference points	Download PDF	7	1
lecture40	Harvest control rules	Download PDF	3	0
lecture50	Case studies	Download PDF	4	0

Tutorial 6: Principles of utilisation: The precautionary approach

2.7 Methods and applications for data-limited fisheries

2.7.1 Purpose

This tutorial is found as the seventh tutorial in <http://tutor-web.net/fish/fish850>. During the FarFish project, this tutorial will be developed to contain an extensive tutorial on methods for data-limited fisheries. This tutorial will build on the population dynamics modelling techniques introduced in earlier tutorials and study issues that arise when applying to data-limited fisheries.

2.7.2 Prerequisites

This is considered a graduate-level course and will depend on all the previous tutorials in the course.

2.7.3 Current content

During the FarFish project, this tutorial will be developed to contain an extensive tutorial on methods for data-limited fisheries. This tutorial will build on the population dynamics modelling techniques introduced in earlier tutorials and study issues that arise when applying to data-limited fisheries.

The tutorial will teach and use the DLMTool package (<http://www.datalimitedtoolkit.org/>), to be used elsewhere in the FarFish project also.

It will also include use of the R Shiny package, by further developing tools from FP7 project MareFrame and H2020 project MINOUW. A part of the new development will allow the user to upload their own data and be asked questions on statistical analyses, personalised and from their own data set.

2.7.4 Drills

Each lecture will contain one or more drills on the topics of the lecture.

Currently the tutorial contains a total of 0 drills.

Contents **View** Edit Sharing Actions ▾ Display ▾ Add new... ▾ State: Published ▾

Methods and applications for data-limited fisheries (fish850.1)

by admin — last modified 2017-11-27 15:13 — [History](#)

Take a drill on Effects of limited data Download tutorial notes

Lectures Literature Related courses Data files

- [Show raw tutorial TeX](#)
- [Update tutorial PDF](#)

Code	Name	Slide download
lecture0100	Effects of limited data	
lecture0200	Appropriate models and statistical methods for limited data scenarios	
lecture0300	The DLMTTool package	
lecture0400	Case studies	

Tutorial 7: Methods and applications for data-limited fisheries

3 Conclusions and discussions

A course outline has been set up in accordance with the description of Deliverable 7.3. The outline consists of tutorials required for a course on fish population dynamics and utilisation in an ecosystem context in the case of data-limited fisheries.

References

Jonsdottir, A.H., Bjornsdottir, A. & Stefansson, G. 2017. Difference in learning among students doing pen-and-paper homework compared to web-based homework. *J. Statistics Education*. DOI: 10.1080/10691898.2017.1291289

Lentin, J., Jonsdottir, A.H., Stern, D., Mokua V. and Stefansson, G. 2014. A mobile web for enhancing statistics and mathematics education. First presented at icots9. See <http://arxiv.org/abs/1406.5004> (in prep).

Lentin, J. and Stefansson, G. (2018). From smileys to Smileycoins: Using a cryptocurrency for rewards in education. First presented at SIMC 2017 (submitted to Ledger)

Evelyn Njurai, Gunnar Stefansson, Anna Jónsdóttir, Patrick Mwenda, Mose Obonyo and Joseph Kariuki. 2017. Initial reflections on teaching and learning mathematics using tablet in a prison education centre. First presented at SIMC 2017 (accepted), Nairobi, Kenya.

Stefansson, G. (2004). The tutor-web: An educational system for class-room presentation, evaluation and self-study. *Computers & Education*, 43 (4), 315-343.

G. Stefansson, D.A. Stern, J. Lentin, A.H. Jonsdottir. 2017. Evidence-based technology to enhance mathematics education from Iceland to Kenya. Presented at SIMC 2017 (accepted), Nairobi, Kenya.